

COOPERATIVE LANGUAGE LEARNING APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents teaching strategies and techniques in a quick reference format. Cooperative learning is based on learner-centred method involving the four most important learning cycles as follows the action, reflection, knowledge, planning. This new method of foreign language learning is organized as a conversation between the learners. Communication is considered as a primary purpose and takes place upon certainly agreed set of cooperative rules. In these circumstances students' are managed to accomplish their goals and it gives the positive relationship among other students and also helps them to build healthy social, psychological and cognitive development. It replaces competition with cooperation through interactive activities including the stress reduction. This method helps you to use a target language without second thought or translating in your native language; learners play more active roles and act as recourses of each other.

Keywords: English learning, cooperation, communication, learners, foreign language

Introduction

Cooperative Learning (CCL) is part of general instructional approach also known as Collaborative Learning. This approach makes maximum use of cooperative activities involving pairs and small groups of learners in the classroom. It has been defined as exchange of information between learners in groups and in which each learner is held accountable for his or her own learning and is motivated to increase the learning of others. Cooperative Learning in this context sought to do the following:

- Raise of achievements of all students;
- Positive relationships among students;
- Experience on healthy social, psychological, and cognitive development;

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- Replace competition for cooperation;
- Replace teacher-fronted lessons for student-centred.

Goals of Cooperative Language Learning

- To provide opportunities for naturalistic second language acquisition through the use of interactive pair and group activities.
- To provide teachers with a methodology to enable them to achieve this goal and one that can be applied in a variety of curriculum settings (e.g., content-based, foreign language classrooms);
- To enable focused attention to particular lexical items, language structures, and communicative functions through the use of interactive tasks;
- To provide opportunities for learners to develop successful learning and communication strategies;
- To enhance learner motivation and reduce learner stress and to create a positive affective classroom climate.

Approach – Theory of Language

We outlined “interactive” view of language structure.

Cooperative language learning is built on these premises in several ways:

This involves using a progressive format or sequencing of strategies in the conversation class which carefully prepare students, that systematically breaks down the stereotypes of classroom procedure and allows them to begin interacting democratically and independently through this approach students learn step-by-step functional interaction techniques at the same time the group spirit or trust in being build. Practices that attempt to organize second language teaching/learning according to these premises, explicitly or implicitly are jointly labeled Cooperative Language Learning. In its application CCL is used to support both structural and functional models as well as interactional models of language since CCL activities may be used to focus on language form as well as to practice particular language functions.

Learners Role

The primary role of the learner is as member who must work collaboratively on tasks with other group members; learners have to learn teamwork skills. Learners are also directors of their own learning. They are taught to plan, monitor and evaluate their own learning. Learning is something that requires students' active involvement and participation pair grouping is the most typical CCL format, ensuring the maximum amount of time and they are engaged during classroom. Pair tasks: per-tutoring and peer-monitoring, checkers and information shares.

Teachers Role

Create a highly structured and well organized learning environment in the classroom: Setting goals, planning and structuring tasks, establishing the physical arrangement of the classroom, Assigning students to groups and roles, and selecting materials and time (Johnson et al. 1994). Be a facilitator of learning.

Conclusions

The use of discussion groups, group work, and pair work has often been advocated both in teaching languages and in other subjects. Typically, such groups are used to provide a change from the normal pace of classroom events and to increase the amount of student participation in lessons. Such activities are not necessarily cooperative. In Cooperative Learning, group activities are the major mode of learning and are part of a comprehensive theory and system for the use of group work in teaching. Group activities are carefully planned to maximize students' interaction and to facilitate students' contributions to each other's learning. CLL activities can also be used in collaboration with other teaching methods and approaches. Unlike most language teaching proposals, CLL has been extensively researched and evaluated and research findings are generally supportive), although little of this research was conducted in L2 classrooms. CLL is not without its critics, however. Some have questioned its use with learners of different proficiency levels, suggesting that some groups of students) e.g., intermediate and advanced learners) may obtain more benefits from it than others. In addition, it places considerable demand on teachers, who may have difficulty, adapting to the new roles required of them. Proponents of CLL stress that it enhances both learning and learners' interaction skills.

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